

Graphical Abstract

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Abstract

Hypothesis: The interfacial free energy between hydrate and water phases is a key thermodynamic parameter that governs both nucleation kinetics and crystal growth of gas hydrates. In these strategic materials—crystalline inclusion compounds where hydrogen-bonded water cages encapsulate small guest molecules such as methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂)—this interfacial energy plays a crucial role in determining phase stability and formation pathways. Given the significance of gas hydrates in energy storage, CO₂ sequestration, and climate-related processes, accurately determining their interfacial energies is essential for advancing both fundamental understanding and technological applications. Despite its importance, the hydrate–water interfacial energy remains poorly constrained due to substantial experimental uncertainties and the limitations of indirect estimation methods. For example, reported experimental values for CH₄ hydrate span a wide range from 28 to 40 mJ/m². Interestingly, some studies suggest these values are comparable to the interfacial free energy of the hexagonal ice (ice Ih)–water interface, approximately 32 mJ/m², hinting at potential analogies between clathrate hydrate and ice interfaces.

Calculations: In this work, we present a direct molecular simulation of the CH₄ hydrate–water interfacial free energy using two novel and independent extensions of the mold integration method. These extensions are specifically designed to induce the formation of a thin, planar hydrate–water interface and to compute the reversible work required to create it. For this purpose, we employ the TIP4P/Ice force field—one of the most reliable water models available—known for accurately reproducing the melting temperature of ice Ih under ambient conditions.

Findings: Our results show that the interfacial free energy of CH₄ hydrate is significantly higher than that of CO₂ hydrate, offering a natural explanation for their markedly different nucleation behaviors. This aligns with prior predictions based on Classical Nucleation Theory, as well as advanced sampling techniques such as Transition Path Sampling and Transition Interface Sampling. Notably, our computed value for CH₄ hydrate approaches ~ 40 mJ/m², in agreement with the upper bound of existing experimental estimates, while values for CO₂ hydrate and ice Ih remain closer to ~ 30 mJ/m². This direct, theory-independent determination provides new insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying hydrate formation and offers robust benchmarks for predictive modeling and the design of hydrate-based technologies.

Keywords:

Interfacial free energy, methane hydrate, hydrate–water interface, computer simulation

1. Introduction

In the late 1700s, while investigating the solubility of newly discovered “airs” (gases), several natural philosophers observed the unexpected formation of ice-like solids—even at temperatures above the freezing point of water—when certain gases were bubbled through cold water or when such mixtures were frozen. Sir Humphry Davy, a pioneer of electrochemistry and mentor to Michael Faraday, later identified these substances as compounds formed by water and gas, coining the term “gas hydrates”. After more than a century of continued study, these materials were ultimately recognized as clathrates: crystalline structures in which small guest molecules are trapped within

a hydrogen-bonded lattice of water cages, as is the case for methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) under suitable thermodynamic conditions [1?, 2].

Notably, clathrate structures have also been identified in intermetallic [3, 4], in which metallic guest ions are encapsulated by frameworks of group 14 elements (Si, Ge, or Sn). More recently, clathrate-like architectures have been shown to self-assemble from colloidal particles [5, 6], opening new possibilities for the formation of larger cages and enabling mesoscale phenomena with potential relevance to biological and photonic applications.

A key common point between traditional gas hydrates and more challenging and sophisticated clathrates is the host–guest interaction, which underpins their use in natural gas capture [?] and gas storage [7]. Methane hydrates, in particular, have garnered significant attention as an alternative energy resource due

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to their vast natural deposits [2, 8?–15]. Additionally, hydrates play a critical role in climate dynamics, as they represent a major reservoir of greenhouse gases that could be destabilized under changing environmental conditions [2, 8, 9, 16?–18]. Beyond energy and climate, gas hydrates are also being explored for their potential in CO₂ sequestration [19–21], as well as for gas storage [22] and transportation technologies [23–25].

A comprehensive understanding of the thermodynamic mechanisms governing hydrate nucleation and growth is essential for the effective exploitation of gas hydrates [2, 26?–51]. The simplest but also primary theoretical framework to understand homogeneous nucleation of hydrates is Classical Nucleation Theory (CNT) [26]. According to the CNT, two parameters mainly govern the nucleation process: the nucleation driving force and the interfacial free energy between the hydrate and water. An accurate knowledge of these two key properties is necessary for a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms governing hydrate nucleation. Unfortunately, this is not an easy task. Although obtaining accurate values for the nucleation driving force is inherently challenging, reliable estimates can often be derived from indirect experimental observations and analyses [27]. Molecular simulations have become an invaluable tool for quantifying nucleation driving forces in both pure substances and hydrate-forming systems [49, 50, 52–55].

However, there is no universally accepted or standardized experimental method for determining solid–fluid interfacial free energies [57], in contrast to the well-established techniques available for fluid–fluid interfaces [58, 59]. One of the employed methods for estimating solid–liquid interfacial free energy is based on the classical Young’s equation [60]. Solid–fluid interfacial free energies can also be estimated using the Gibbs–Thomson relation [61–63]. Uchida *et al.* [64, 65] and Anderson *et al.* [66, 67] independently reported interfacial free energies of $\gamma_{hw} = 39, 34(6),$ and $32(3)$ mJ/m² for CH₄ hydrate and $28(6)$ and $30(3)$ mJ/m² for CO₂ hydrate using this technique, respectively. In all cases, uncertainties are large due to limitations of the methodology. Some publications indicate that these values closely match the interfacial free energy of the hexagonal ice (ice Ih)–water interface, approximately 32 mJ/m², suggesting analogous interfacial behavior between clathrate hydrates and ice [34, 36, 64–67]. However, new nucleation rate calculations of CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates published during the last five years indicate that this may not be the case [43, 45, 46, 48–50, 68–70]. This is a crucial topic that warrants thorough analysis, as γ_{hw} plays a pivotal role in determining hydrate nucleation and growth [2, 26?].

Computer simulations offer an interesting alternative way to predict solid–fluid interfacial free energies in cases where experiments are scarce. A comprehensive and up-to-date discussion of the most relevant computer simulation methodologies is presented in detail in a recent review article authored by some of us [71]. CNT [72–75], combined with the Seeding approach [36, 52, 54], is the only indirect computational methodology reported in the literature for determining the interfacial free energies of hydrates.

Jacobson and Molinero performed the first indirect calculation of the CH₄ hydrate–water interfacial free energy [34].

They performed Seeding simulations of a slab of an M liquid (a single particle with properties intermediate between CH₄ and CO₂ [31, 76]) in contact with a saturated water solution with M, containing clusters of M hydrates of different sizes to determine the melting temperatures of the crystalline nuclei. Combining these results with the well-known Gibbs–Thomson relationship [61–63], they obtained a value $\gamma_{hw} \approx 36(2)$ mJ/m² that lies between the experimental value for the CO₂ hydrate–water interface and that for the CH₄ hydrate–water interfacial energy. One year later, Knott *et al.* [36] also predicted an interfacial free energy value of the CH₄ hydrate $\gamma_{hw} \approx 31$ mJ/m² using similar technique.

More recently, some of us have investigated the nucleation of CH₄ hydrate using molecular dynamics simulations combining the Seeding technique [36, 52, 54] and CNT [73–75]. From these simulations, an interfacial free energy of approximately 38 mJ/m² was determined at 400 bar and 260 K, corresponding to a supercooling of about 35 K below the three-phase equilibrium temperature [48, 77]. We have also employed the same techniques and molecular model for water to estimate the nucleation rate of CO₂ hydrate under the same pressure and supercooling conditions [70, 78]. Our results indicate that the corresponding interfacial free energy is approximately 22 mJ/m². Although these values correspond to the interfacial free energy of both hydrates at supercooling conditions (35 K), they represent a difference of 16 mJ/m² of interfacial energy between both hydrate–water interfaces.

The estimation of interfacial free energies is intrinsically connected to the quantification of hydrate nucleation rates. Arjun and Bolhuis have examined the homogeneous nucleation of CO₂ and CH₄ hydrates using rigorous molecular simulation techniques, including Transition Path Sampling and Transition Interface Sampling [43, 45, 46, 68, 69]. The key finding is that the nucleation barrier for CO₂ hydrate is lower by several tens of $k_B T$ compared to that of CH₄ hydrate under similar conditions [46]. In line with this, our recent findings exhibit the same trend [48, 50, 70, 77] which we ascribe to differences in the interfacial free energies between the two hydrate systems.

A fundamental question remains: Are the interfacial free energies of CO₂ hydrate–water and CH₄ hydrate–water indeed different, as suggested by indirect methods, or are they comparable? Notably, all aforementioned estimates rely on indirect approaches. A more definitive answer could be obtained by employing a direct method to compute the interfacial free energies of both hydrates, thereby clarifying whether γ_{hw} differs between these systems.

The direct methods [71, 79–92] allow for evaluation directly, without any theoretical approach, solid–fluid interfacial free energies in a straightforward manner. The Mold Integration (MI) technique is the only direct method successfully used to predict with confidence the interfacial free energy of hydrate–water interfaces [71, 78, 93–95]. Fig. 1 shows schematically the basis of this methodology, which allows to identify water molecules in the hydrate phase, to induce the formation of a hydrate–water interface, and to reversibly estimate the work to form the interface and the interfacial free energy from thermodynamic integration. This technique has allowed us to accurately estimate CO₂

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the MI technique. A collection of associating sites (cyan spheres) is placed at the crystallographic positions of the oxygen atoms in the hydrate lattice to induce the formation of hydrate–water interfaces (middle). Methane and water molecules are represented as green spheres and white and red sticks, respectively. The growth of the hydrate phase is tracked by monitoring the number of water molecules (left) identified as solid-like using an extension of the Lechner–Dellago local bond order parameter allowing to identify if the crystallization takes place as soon as the simulation begins (top left), requires an induction time (middle-left), or never happens (bottom-left) [56]. The interfacial free energy is estimated by integrating the site-filling curve where the crystallization never takes place (bottom right) via Eq. (1), in conjunction with the thermodynamic definition given in Eq. (2), where γ_{hw} is obtained by extrapolating to the optimal radius (top right).

hydrate-water and THF-water interfacial free energies [78, 93–95].

In this work, we apply two extensions of the MI method [78, 93] to obtain independent estimates of the CH_4 hydrate–water interfacial free energy. This approach enables us to calculate γ_{hw} directly from its thermodynamic definition, without relying on theoretical models or additional computations. We present, for the first time, a direct calculation of the interfacial free energy for the CH_4 hydrate–water system using this approach. The resulting values are compared with those from our earlier studies based on robust indirect methodologies [49, 70].

2. Simulation methods

2.1. Methodology

The MI technique is based on the use of a mold of attractive interaction sites located at the crystallographic positions of one or several planes of the solid phase involved in the calculation of the interfacial free energy [96–98]. The interaction between the molecules of the fluid system and the attractive interaction sites is based on a continuous version of the square-well potential [99]. In hydrates, it is possible to use two different types

of molds of attractive interaction sites: one located at the crystallographic positions of the oxygen atoms of the molecules of water in the hydrate (MI-H) [78] and other at the centers of the voids of each cage left by the hydrate structure (MI-G) [93]. See a representation of the initial configurations of the simulation boxes in Fig. S5 of the SI.

The attractive interaction sites of the mold are switched on gradually to induce the formation of a solid hydrate slab in the fluid at coexistence conditions. The energy needed to form a thin crystal slab of the solid phase in the fluid phase can be computed by integrating the average number of filled attractive interaction sites (wells), $N_{fw}(\epsilon)$, along a reversible thermodynamic path that links the fluid system without the solid hydrate slab (wells off), and the fluid system with the induced hydrate slab (wells completely on) [78, 93, 96]:

$$\Delta G^{hw} = N_w \epsilon_m - \int_0^{\epsilon_m} \langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP, \mathcal{AT}} d\epsilon \quad (1)$$

where N_w is the number of wells in the mold, and ϵ and ϵ_m are the well depth and the maximum well depth, respectively, of the square-well potential. The average number of filled wells is obtained in the isothermal-isobaric ensemble to ensure that the system is always at the selected coexistence conditions of

T and P . \mathcal{A} represents the interfacial area between the hydrate and the aqueous solution of CH_4 . Knowledge of ΔG^{hw} allows to determine the solid-fluid interfacial free energy γ_{hw} in a simple way,

$$\gamma_{hw} = \frac{\Delta G^{hw}}{2\mathcal{A}} \quad (2)$$

Factor 2 arises because two hydrate-fluid interfaces appear when the solid hydrate slab is induced. We refer the lector to our previous works [78, 93, 94] and Section 4.3 for further details.

2.2. Model

Water molecules are modeled using the well-known TIP4P/Ice [100], CH_4 molecules are modeled using a spherical Lennard-Jones (LJ) interaction site with the parameters proposed by Guillot and Guissani [101] and Paschek [102], Note that although CH_4 is a nonspherical molecule [103], this simple model has been used previously in the literature to determine the dissociation line of CH_4 hydrate in pure water [104–107] and in salty water at oceanic conditions [108], the solubility of CH_4 in water [48], and homogeneous nucleation rate of CH_4 hydrate formation [49]. The unlike interactions between water and CH_4 molecules are taken into account using the well-known Lorentz-Berthelot combining rules. The use of these rules ensures a good description of the dissociation line of the CH_4 hydrate, as well as other properties [48, 49, 104, 105, 107]. Particularly, this election provides a good estimation of the dissociation temperature of the methane hydrate at 400 bar using the direct coexistence technique, $T_3 = 294(2)$ K, and the solubility methodology, $T_3 = 295(2)$ K, recently used by Grabowska *et al.* [48]. This result is in excellent agreement with the experimental value, 297 K [?]. Note that a good estimate of the dissociation line of the hydrate is necessary to use with confidence the MI approach [78, 93, 94, 96, 98].

2.3. Simulation details

We use the GROMACS simulation package [109] to perform MD simulations via the isothermal-isobaric or $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble [110–114] at 400 bar and 294 K using the MI-H [78] and MI-G [93] techniques. We put 736 water molecules surrounded by two pure liquid CH_4 phases with 128 molecules in each one in the initial simulation box. We choose arbitrary this direction as z -axis being the xy -plane parallel to the interfaces. The dimensions of the simulation boxes along the x and y -axis parallel to the water–methane planar interface are chosen to be consistent with the size of the CH_4 hydrate unit cell formed when the mold is switched on. The simulation box is a parallelepiped of volume $V = L_x \times L_y \times L_z$, where L_x , L_y , and L_z are the dimensions of the simulation box. L_x and L_y are kept constant, and only L_z is varied along the simulation to keep the pressure constant along the direction perpendicular to the planar interfaces. We first simulate a bulk CH_4 hydrate phase using the anisotropic version of the NPT ensemble at the equilibrium conditions under study. From this simulation is possible to determine the equilibrium dimensions of the simulation box (L_x , L_y , and L_z).

This ensures that the slab of hydrate induced by the mold, at the equilibrium conditions of pressure and temperature, is non-stressed [111–113].

Newton’s equations are solved using the Verlet leapfrog algorithm [115]. We use a time step of 2 fs. All simulations are run in the $NP_z\mathcal{A}T$ ensemble to ensure that the pressure and the temperature are kept constant. The Nosé-Hoover thermostat [116] and the Parrinello-Rahman barostat [117] are used to keep both the temperature and the pressure constants. Simulations of the bulk solid phase to determine the equilibrium dimensions of the simulation box are run using the anisotropic version of the Parrinello-Rahman barostat. In all cases, we use 2 and 1 ps for the relaxation times in the thermostat and barostat, respectively. We use a cutoff radius for both dispersive and electrostatic interactions of 1 nm. Long-range interactions due to electrostatic interactions are determined using the Particle-Mesh Ewald technique [118]. We do not use long-range corrections for the dispersive interactions. The LINCS algorithm is used in order to fix the molecular geometry.

For the calculation of the interfacial free energy we use $N_w = 56$ attractive sites with $\varepsilon_m = 8 k_B T$ (MI-H) [78] and $N_w = 16$ attractive sites with $\varepsilon_m = 12 k_B T$ (MI-G) [93]. We have chosen the same geometries used in our previous works to estimate the interfacial free energy of the CO_2 hydrate-water interface [78, 93, 94]. The attractive sites of both molds are used to induce the formation of a CH_4 hydrate slab in the middle of the simulation box. Fig. S3 of SI shows two snapshots of the initial simulation box with the mold used in this work.

3. Results and discussion

The MI methodology allows to determine the interfacial free energy in three steps [78, 93, 94, 96, 98]: (1) estimation of the optimal radius r_w^0 ; (2) calculation of the reversible work needed to form a thin crystal slab of the solid phase in the fluid phase and γ_{hw} at least three radii higher than the optimal one; and (3) extrapolation of γ_{hw} at r_w^0 . This procedure is explained in the following sections.

3.1. r_w^0 estimation

The accurate determination of r_w^0 requires multiple simulations. By analyzing the behavior of the system for a series of different values of r_w , it is possible to find three different scenarios as a function of the r_w value. If $r_w < r_w^0$, the fluid phase becomes unstable and the fluid system crystallizes as soon as the simulation starts (scenario I) [78, 93, 94]. Fig. 2 presents the final configurations obtained from simulations employing both MI approaches, highlighting crystallization induced by molds activated with $r_w < r_w^0$. Representative snapshots from different stages of the simulations are shown in Figs. S1 and S2 of the Supporting Information (SI). Additionally, movies S1 and S2 illustrate the crystallization process observed with two extensions of the Mold Integration technique, the Mold Integration-Host (MI-H) and Mold Integration-Guest (MI-G) methods, under conditions where $r_w < r_w^0$. See Section 4 for further details. If $r_w > r_w^0$, and the value of r_w is closed to the optimal value, r_w^0 ,

Figure 2: Representation of the final configurations of simulation boxes using the MI-H (top) and the MI-G (bottom) approaches when $r_w < r_w^0$ at 400 bar and 294 K. In both cases, CH₄ molecules and water molecules are represented as green spheres and red and white sticks, respectively. Cyan and purple spheres represent the attractive interaction sites used in the MI-H and MI-G methods, respectively.

the system can overcome the energy barrier and crystallize after a relatively short period of time called induction period (scenario II). The larger the r_w value, the larger the time required by the system to crystallize. If r_w is large enough, the system will not crystallize because the energy barrier that the system has to overcome is too large (scenario III). Movies S3 and S4 of SI demonstrate that crystallization does not occur with either method when $r_w < r_w^0$. The optimal r_w^0 value is found in the frontier between scenarios I and II. Five independent trajectories have been run for each r_w in both methods at each r_w analyzed. Simulations have run for 500 ns to identify the behavior of the system, at each r_w , with one of the three possible scenarios explained previously.

To study the behavior of the system as a function of the r_w value, it is necessary to identify the number of molecules of water that transit from the aqueous fluid phase to the crystal hydrate phase. The number of molecules of water in the hydrate phase, as a function of the simulation time, $n_h = n_h(t)$, is analyzed using the local bond order parameters proposed by Lechner and Dellago [56] once the simulation has finished. In particular, the \bar{q}_3 parameter has been chosen to distinguish between liquid-like and CH₄ hydrate-like water molecules. This parameter has been previously used by some of us in our previous works about the CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy [78, 93, 94]. For further technical details, we recommend our previous works [78, 93, 94] and our recent results extending this technique to deal with other hydrate structures [95, 119].

We first consider the election of the optimal r_w^0 value using

the MI-H technique (see Section 4). As can be seen in Fig. S3 of the SI, it is possible to identify the three mentioned scenarios as a function of r_w from the analysis of n_h . When $r_w \leq 0.792$ Å, the system crystallizes as soon as the simulations start, and consequently, these values. When $r_w \geq 0.855$ Å, large induction periods can be observed in at least one of the runs, and the behavior of the system can be categorized as the expected one in scenario II ($r_w > r_w^0$). Finally, when $r_w \geq 0.887$ Å, the system can not overcome the energy barrier, and no crystallization is observed as it is expected when $r_w \gg r_w^0$. This is the expected behavior found in scenario III. From this analysis, it is clear that the choice of $r_w = 0.823$ Å as the optimal value, r_w^0 , since the change from scenario I and II is observed at exactly this value of r_w . Since free-energy calculations are extremely complex, in order to ensure that r_w^0 and, hence, γ_{lw} , are calculated with the appropriate uncertainty, a conservative range for r_w^0 has been chosen. In this case, the optimal value and its uncertainty is $r_w^0 = 0.823(95)$ Å.

We follow a similar analysis to identify the three possible scenarios as a function of r_w using the MI-G methodology (see Section 4). As can be observed in Fig. S4 of the SI, the behavior of the system as a function of r_w is similar to that observed in Fig. S3 (SI) for the case of the MI-H method. Following the same approach, the final optimal value is $r_w^0 = 0.681(95)$ Å.

3.2. Thermodynamic integration

Interfacial energy can not be evaluated directly at $r_w = r_w^0$ because there is no energy barrier between the aqueous and the

Figure 3: Averaged number of filled attractive sites, $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_zAT}$, as a function of the well depth ϵ , obtained from MI-H at $r_w = 0.8867 \text{ \AA}$ (top) and MI-G at $r_w = 1.1084 \text{ \AA}$ (bottom) at 400 bar and 294 K. In both cases, in the main figure, the symbols represent the values of $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_zAT}$ from the NP_zT simulations, and the curves are obtained by fitting the simulation results. The insets represent the rest of the curves obtained for each r_w value used in both MI-H and MI-G methods. The value of r_w at which each curve has been obtained is shown in the legend.

hydrate phase, i.e., the system can freely crystallize, crossing a first-order transition and moving away from the coexistence equilibrium. In order to create a thermodynamic path between the fluid without a solid hydrate slab (mold off) and the fluid with the solid hydrate slab (mold on), it is necessary to ensure that a phase transition does not occur. As Espinosa *et al.* [96] pointed out in their original work, it is necessary to perform the thermodynamic integration for $r_w > r_w^0$. This ensures the reversibility of the system, a necessary condition to calculate γ_{hw} .

In order to calculate ΔG^{hw} , we determine the average number of filled attractive sites, $\langle N_{fw} \rangle$, as function of the attractive interaction between the mold and the particles of the fluid system, ϵ . $\langle N_{fw} \rangle$ can be calculated by performing simulations in the isothermic-isobaric ensemble for different values of ϵ from 0 to ϵ_m ($\epsilon_m = 8 k_B T$ and $\epsilon_m = 12 k_B T$ for MI-H and MI-G techniques, respectively). Particularly, to accurately obtain $\langle N_{fw} \rangle$ as a function of ϵ , we perform between 17 and 21 simulations

in the NP_zT ensemble depending if the MI-H or the MI-G technique is used. Each simulation is equilibrated during 20 ns and averages are calculated over 80 ns. Fig. 3 shows $\langle N_{fw} \rangle$, as functions of ϵ , as obtained from simulation results for the r_w values using both methodologies. We have also included the fitted curves in all the cases. As can be seen, when the mold is completely activated, the $\langle N_{fw} \rangle$ value at each r_w is equal to the total number of attractive sites located in the mold, N_w [96].

The difference in energy between the fluid state in which the mold is off ($\epsilon = 0$) and the state in which the associating sites of the mold are completely activated ($\epsilon = \epsilon_m$) has two contributions: one because of the creation of the hydrate-fluid interfaces and other due to the interaction between the mold and the molecules (water or methane depending on the MI technique used) in the system. The first contribution can be easily obtained from the integration of the fitted curves shown in Fig. 3 from $\epsilon = 0$ to $\epsilon = \epsilon_m$, according to equations presented in Section 4. The second one, which accounts for the mold-molecule interaction energy ($-N_w \epsilon_m$) of the final state (mold completely activated or $\epsilon = \epsilon_m$), can be easily subtracted from the thermodynamic integration contribution. Finally, once ΔG^{hw} has been calculated, the value of γ_{hw} for each r_w value can be easily obtained according to explanations given in Section 4.

3.3. γ_{hw} calculation

As it has been explained in previous sections, when $r_w > r_w^0$, there exists yet an energy barrier that the system has to overcome in order to crystallize. It is necessary to obtain the value of γ_{hw} when $r_w = r_w^0$. Fig. 4 shows the interfacial free energy, as a function of r_w , obtained from MI-H and MI-G techniques. As can be seen, γ_{hw} behaves linearly with the range of the associating sites of the mold. Particularly, it is possible to calculate the real value of γ_{hw} by extrapolating the results as $r_w \rightarrow r_w^0$. It is important to mention that this behavior has been previously observed with different systems [55, 78, 93–98, 120]. In all cases, MI provides interfacial free energies in excellent agreement with the experimental data.

According to the results presented in Fig. 4, the values of γ_{hw} obtained when $r_w \rightarrow r_w^0$ using both techniques are 43(2) and 44(1) mJ/m², respectively. As can be observed, the results obtained using the two techniques are in excellent agreement with each other. It is essential to emphasize that the results presented should be regarded as independent, as the key parameters employed in each method – namely, N_w , r_w , and ϵ_m – differ, as discussed in detail in Section 4.

It is possible to compare the predicted CH₄ hydrate-water γ_{hw} values obtained from simulation with experimental data obtained by Uchida *et al.* [64, 65], 39 and 34(6) mJ/m². Note that both values are the same within the statistical uncertainty, although there exists a difference of 5 mJ/m² between both results. Anderson *et al.* [66, 67] have also independently determined γ_{hw} values using the same indirect technique and thermodynamic relationship: between 32(1) and 35(1) mJ/m², given a final value of 32(3) mJ/m². In summary, all the CH₄ hydrate-water interfacial free energy values obtained from experiments range in the interval from 28 to 40 mJ/m². This is a huge range of values and contrasts with the accuracy of the measurements

Figure 4: CH₄ hydrate-water γ_{hw} as a function of r_w obtained from MI-H and MI-G methods at 400 bar and 294 K. Blue circles and green squares correspond to the results of γ_{hw} obtained from the thermodynamic integration from MI-H and MI-G, respectively. Blue and green dashed lines represent the fitted line of γ_{hw} as a function of r_w for MI-H and MI-G, respectively. Finally, the red diamond and pink triangle are the result of γ_{hw} obtained when $r_w = r_w^0$ from MI-H and MI-G, respectively

available in the literature for the interfacial tension of liquid water at ambient conditions, 72 mJ/m², showing that the experimental determination of solid-fluid interfacial energies is a difficult task [57–59].

Simulation data obtained in this work, 43(2) and 44(1) mJ/m², seem to overestimate the experimental data taken from the literature. It is necessary to recall that this result overestimates the experimental value provided by Anderson and collaborators but is very close to one of the experimental values obtained by Uchida and coworkers, 39 mJ/m². This is the first time the Mold Integration methodology, a direct computer simulation method used to predict interfacial free energies of a wide variety of different model and realist systems [71], seems not to fully reproduce the experimental hydrate-fluid interfacial energies. Is the CH₄ hydrate-water interfacial system the limit of applicability of the Mold Integration method? We think the answer is no and will try to justify why.

To answer this question, we first compare the simulation results obtained from the MI direct technique with values previously obtained in the literature using indirect computer simulation methods. Jacobson and Molinero [34], using the mW water model [121], estimated a value of $\gamma_{hw} \approx 36(2)$ mJ/m². Note that this value corresponds to the case of a hydrate in which the guest molecule has intermediate properties between CH₄ and CO₂. This value lies between the experimental value for the CO₂ hydrate-water interface [67], 32(3) mJ/m², and that for the CH₄ hydrate-water interfacial energy [64], 39 mJ/m². This suggests that γ_{hw} is closer to 40 than to 30 mJ/m². One year later, Knott *et al.* [36] obtained a value for the interfacial free energy, $\gamma_{hw} = 31$ mJ/m².

However, one must be careful with the predictions obtained using this water model to predict γ_{hw} values. Although the suc-

cessful mW model can predict a great variety of properties and systems, the original version of the mW model is parameterized to match the experimental vaporization enthalpy, liquid water density, and hexagonal ice melting temperature [122]. It is important to recall in this context that the prediction of hydrate – water interfacial free energy values critically depends on an accurate determination of the hydrate – water – guest three-phase equilibrium temperature. However, this model is found to overestimate the melting temperature of methane hydrate by ~ 15 –20 K [31, 123, 124]. Particularly, Jin and Zhong [124] have recently reparameterized the mW model to accurately predict the experimental phase diagram of methane hydrate. They have shown that the phase stability of methane hydrate depends on the spring constant λ of the mW model, which determines the strength of the tetrahedral angle formed by three water molecules in the mW model. It would be interesting in the future to determine the CH₄ hydrate – water interfacial free energy using the parametrization proposed by these authors.

It is clear that previous works in the literature suggest that the hydrate-water interfacial energy of the CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates are similar and also around the value of the ice-water interfacial energy, ~ 30 mJ/m² [34, 64–67]. However, our current results indicate that the CH₄ hydrate-water γ_{hw} value is substantially higher than that of the CO₂ hydrate – water interface, in agreement with estimations from their nucleation rates [70, 77]. In the next section, we compare both results to clarify and understand from a microscopic perspective the reasons for which interfacial free energies of CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates seem to be different.

3.4. Comparison between γ_{hw} values of the CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates

We compare the results of γ_{hw} obtained in this work for the CH₄ hydrate with the results obtained by some of us [78, 93, 94] for the hydrate of CO₂. Fig. 5 shows the CH₄ hydrate- and CO₂ hydrate-water interfacial free energy values, as functions of r_w , obtained from MI-H and MI-G techniques. In both systems, the interfacial free energy between the hydrates and the aqueous phase has been obtained at 400 bar and coexistence conditions.

As can be seen, the γ_{hw} values obtained in this work for the CH₄ hydrate, 43(2) and 44(1) mJ/m², are about 40% higher than that for the CO₂ hydrate at practically the similar thermodynamic conditions (29(2), 30(2) and 31(2) mJ/m²) [78, 93, 94]. Is this real? To check this hypothesis, we compare these results with estimations provided by the Seeding combined with CNT approach using the same molecular models and under the same conditions of temperature and pressure for CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates.

Although the reader can see the results in both publications, to clarify the main result, we summarize the most essential conclusions obtained by these authors. According to CNT, the homogenous nucleation rate can be expressed as [27, 29, 30, 70, 77, 125],

$$J = \rho_G Z f^+ e^{-\Delta G_c/k_B T} = J_0 e^{-\Delta G_c/k_B T} \quad (3)$$

where ρ_G is the guest (CO₂ or CH₄) density in the aqueous solution phase, Z the Zelkovich factor, f^+ the attachment rate or

Figure 5: CH₄ (top results) and CO₂ (bottom results) hydrate-water γ_{hw} as a function of r_w obtained from MI-H and MI-G methods at 400 bar, 294 K (CH₄), and 287 K (CO₂). Blue circles and green squares correspond to the results of γ_{hw} obtained from the thermodynamic integration from MI-H and MI-G, respectively. Blue and green dashed lines represent the fitted line of γ_{hw} as a function of r_w for MI-H and MI-G, respectively. Finally, the red diamond and pink triangle are the result of γ_{hw} obtained when $r_w = r_w^0$ from MI-H and MI-G, respectively. Results for the CO₂ hydrate are taken from our previous works [78, 93, 94].

rate at which CO₂ and CH₄ molecules in the aqueous phase attach to a growing solid cluster, and ΔG_c the nucleation barrier. Following the thermodynamic formalisms of Gibbs [126], the Zeldovich factor Z and the nucleation barrier ΔG_c , can be easily expressed in terms of the driving force for nucleation, $\Delta\mu_N$, and the size of critical solid clusters in both hydrates, N_c ,

$$Z = \sqrt{\frac{|\Delta\mu_N|}{6\pi k_B T N_c}} \quad (4)$$

and

$$\Delta G_c = \frac{1}{2} N_c |\Delta\mu_N| \quad (5)$$

Vega and collaborators [48, 49] and Blas and collaborators [50, 70] have determined, at the same pressure, 400 bar, and supercooling temperature, 35 K, all the parameters included in Eqs. (3)–(5). Table 1 summarizes the parameters that determine homogeneous nucleation rates of both hydrates.

The kinetic prefactor of the nucleation rate in Eq. (3), $J_0 = \rho_G Z f^+$, can be easily obtained from data presented in Table 1. According to this, the J_0 value for both hydrates only exhibits a difference of one order of magnitude since $J_0 \sim 10^{35}$ and $\sim 10^{34} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates, respectively. However, according to the results presented by Grabowska *et al.* [49] and Zerón *et al.* [70], the nucleation rates of the CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates, at the same pressure and supercooling temperature, are $J \sim 10^{-10}$ and $\sim 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. The difference between both nucleation rates is huge. In fact, the nucleation rate of CO₂ hydrate is approximately 35 orders of magnitude larger than that for CH₄ hydrate under the same conditions. What is the reason for this difference?

Parameter	CO ₂ hydrate	CH ₄ hydrate
$\rho_G / (\text{m}^3)$	2.6×10^{27}	3.0×10^{26}
$\rho_H / (\text{m}^3)$	4.7×10^{27}	4.6×10^{27}
N_c^G	20	83
$\Delta\mu_N / k_B T$	-2.26	-2.42
Z	0.077	0.039
f^+ / s	6.5×10^8	1.4×10^9
$\Delta G_c / k_B T$	22.6	100.7
$J / (\text{m}^3 \text{ s})$	2×10^{25}	3×10^{-10}
$\gamma_{hw} (\text{mJ/m}^2)$	18.7	32.5

Table 1: Parameters that control homogeneous nucleation rates of CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates in water: guest density in the aqueous solution, ρ_G , hydrate density, ρ_H , Zeldovich factor, Z , size of the critical solid cluster (in terms of guest molecules), N_c^G , attachment rate, f^+ , nucleation barrier, ΔG_c , driving force for nucleation, $\Delta\mu_N$. We also include homogeneous nucleation rate, J , and hydrate – water interfacial free energy, γ . In all cases, parameters have been obtained at 400 bar and supercooling temperature of 35 K. All the values have been taken from the works of Grabowska *et al.* [77] and Zerón *et al.* [70].

Following Grabowska *et al.* [49] and Zerón *et al.* [70], the difference must stem from the exponential free energy barrier, which consists of two components: $\Delta\mu_N$ and N_c according to Eq. (5). While the $\Delta\mu_N$ values differ and trend in the expected direction, the variation alone does not appear significant enough to account for the disparity in nucleation rates. Instead, the primary factor is N_c , which includes 83 CH₄ molecules but only 20 CO₂ molecules under the same conditions. This distinction is crucial: the critical cluster of CO₂ hydrate is significantly smaller than that of CH₄ hydrate. In terms of free energy barrier values, the differences are huge at the same thermodynamic conditions: the CH₄ hydrate nucleation barrier is $\Delta G_c^{\text{CH}_4} \sim 100 k_B T$ and that of the CO₂ hydrate is $\Delta G_c^{\text{CO}_2} \sim 23 k_B T$. This difference is obviously the reason for the difference in the J values of both hydrates. However, what is the physical origin of this difference? To investigate it, the authors took into account the relationship that describes the nucleation barrier in terms of $\Delta\mu_N$ and the hydrate-water interfacial free energy, γ_{hw} , [70, 77],

$$\Delta G_c = \frac{16\pi\gamma_{hw}^3}{3\rho_H^2 |\Delta\mu_N|} \quad (6)$$

As can be seen, the key to these differing behaviors lies in the interfacial free energy γ_{hw} , which is further amplified as it is raised to the third power. Note that ρ_H and $|\Delta\mu_N|$ values for both hydrate are similar. Particularly, the CO₂ and CH₄ hydrates – water interfacial free energy values obtained by Grabowska *et al.* [77] and Zerón *et al.* [70], using the Seeding technique and CNT are $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CO}_2} = 18.7 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ and $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CH}_4} = 32.5 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. In other words, there exists a difference between both interfacial energies is $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CH}_4} - \gamma_{hw}^{\text{CO}_2} \sim 14 \text{ mJ/m}^2$.

It is interesting to compare this difference with that obtained using the interfacial free energy values of both hydrates obtained using the MI-H and MI-G techniques. According to our previous works [78, 93, 94], $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CO}_2} = 29(2)$, $30(2)$, and $31(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$. One can estimate the mean value for and uncertainty for this interfacial energy (taking into account all the val-

Figure 6: CH₄ (top results) and CO₂ (bottom results) hydrate-water γ_{hw} as a function of r_w obtained from MI-H and MI-G methods. Blue circles and green squares correspond to the results of γ_{hw} obtained from the thermodynamic integration from MI-H and MI-G, respectively. Blue and green dashed lines represent the fitted line of γ_{hw} as a function of r_w for MI-H and MI-G, respectively. Finally, the red diamond and pink triangle are the result of γ_{hw} obtained when $r_w = r_w^0$ from MI-H and MI-G, respectively.

ues) as $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CO}_2} = 30(3) \text{ mJ/m}^2$. Similarly, the interfacial energy of the CH₄ hydrate – water interface obtained in this work is $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CH}_4} = 43(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$. Note that this value and its uncertainty account for the two values previously presented. With this information, one can estimate the difference between both interfacial energies using these direct methods as $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CH}_4} - \gamma_{hw}^{\text{CO}_2} \sim 13(4) \text{ mJ/m}^2$. This is an interesting exercise. However, the values obtained from Seeding and CNT approaches correspond to interfacial energies of spherical hydrate clusters (and not planar hydrate – water interfaces) at supercooling conditions ($\Delta T = 35 \text{ K}$). The γ_{hw} values obtained in this work correspond to planar hydrate – water interfaces at coexistence conditions (hydrate – water – guest), and it is not possible to compare directly both results. Fortunately, as we show in the following paragraphs, it is feasible to estimate $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CH}_4}$ and $\gamma_{hw}^{\text{CO}_2}$ at the same conditions.

The first step is to get the interfacial free energy values of the planar interfaces. Montero de Hijes *et al.* [128] have demonstrated that the solid-fluid interfacial energy varies linearly with $1/R_c$, with R_c the radius of a critical solid cluster obtained from the Seeding technique. Specifically, they identified this relationship across multiple systems, including hard-sphere and Lennard-Jones simplified models, as well as more advanced force fields for water, such as mW and TIP4P/Ice for different supercoolings. In addition, Gabrowska *et al.* [77] and Zerón *et al.* [70] have also found the same behavior for the CH₄ and CO₂ hydrates. This insight has allowed all these authors to estimate, from Seeding calculations and CNT, the interfacial free energy of the corresponding planar solid-fluid interface (but not at coexistence conditions). They extrapolated γ_{hw} to the planar interface ($R_c \rightarrow \infty$) for different γ_{hw} values from different critical solid clusters.

Table 2 shows the values of interfacial energies (for planar interfaces) associated with the CH₄ hydrate – water [77] and

ΔT (K)	γ_{hw} (mJ/m ²)	$\Delta\gamma_{hw}$ (mJ/m ²)
I _h ice – water interface		
0	29.8(2.5)	0
14.5	26.3	-3.5(2.5)
19.5	25.4	-4.4(2.5)
35.5	23.7	-6.1(2.5)
CH ₄ hydrate – water interface		
0	44(2)	0
35	38	-6(2)
CO ₂ hydrate – water interface		
0	30(2)	0
35	22.3	-7.7(2)

Table 2: Estimated Interfacial energy γ_{hw} , as a function of the undercooling ΔT , for I_h ice – water, [127] CH₄ hydrate – water, [77] and CO₂ hydrate – water [70] with planar interface using Seeding-CNT techniques. Values at $\Delta T = 0$ are calculated by MI approach, [78, 93, 94, 98] including those determined in this work. $\Delta\gamma_{hw} = \gamma_{hw}(\Delta T) - \gamma_{hw}(0)$ is the interfacial free energy at supercooling ΔT and at coexistence ($\Delta T = 0 \text{ K}$).

CO₂ hydrate – water [70] interfaces at different supercoolings. For reasons that will be clear in the next paragraph, we have also included the values corresponding I_h ice – water interfacial free energies, at different supercooling values, as obtained from Seeding and CNT calculations by Espinosa *et al.* [127] See the original works of these authors for further details. Table 2 also included the I_h ice – water [98], CH₄ hydrate – water, and CO₂ hydrate water [78, 93, 94] interfacial energy values at coexistence conditions, $\Delta T = 0 \text{ K}$, determined using the Mold Integration technique at coexistence conditions, 29.8(2.5), 43(2), and 30(2) mJ/m², respectively. Note that the value corresponding to the CH₄ hydrate – water interface, 43(2) mJ/m, has been obtained in this work.

We also define $\Delta\gamma_{hw}$ as the difference between $\gamma_{hw}(\Delta T)$, the interfacial free energy at a given supercooling, and $\gamma(0)$, the interfacial free energy at coexistence ($\Delta T = 0 \text{ K}$), obtained from the MI technique for all the systems in Table 2. According to this, $\Delta\gamma_{hw} = \gamma_{hw}(\Delta T) - \gamma_{hw}(0)$, becomes more negative as ΔT increases. The results obtained previously for I_h ice – water by Espinosa *et al.* [98, 127] and for CO₂ hydrates – water [70, 78, 93, 94] follow this trend. Using this information, it is possible to represent $\Delta\gamma_{hw}$, as a function of ΔT , for the systems considered in Table 2. As can be seen in Fig. 6, $\Delta\gamma_{hw}$ shows a linear correlation with ΔT , represented by the continuous magenta line,

$$\Delta\gamma_{hw} = -0.194 \Delta T \text{ (mJ/m}^2\text{)} \quad (7)$$

It is worth noting that the linear regression was performed under the constraint that the line passes through the origin. This is fully justified since $\Delta\gamma_{hw}$ at $\Delta T = 0 \text{ K}$ must vanish since $\gamma_{hw}(\Delta T) \rightarrow \gamma_{hw}(0)$ as $\Delta T \rightarrow 0$. The regression indicates that γ_{hw} decreases $\sim 0.19 \text{ mJ/m}^2$, approximately, for each K, the temperature is decreased with respect to the coexistence temperature. It is easy to check that if we apply it to the CO₂ hydrate – water interface obtained from CNT + Seeding calculations gives the value obtained from the direct MI technique, i.e.,

$\gamma(0) \equiv \gamma_{hw} = \gamma_{hw}(\Delta T) - \Delta\gamma_{hw} = 22.3 + 0.194 \times 35 \approx 29 \text{ mJ/m}^2$, which is in excellent agreement with the value obtained by Blas and collaborators using the MI-H and MI-G methodologies [78, 93, 94], $30(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$. Using the same approach, the estimation of the CH_4 hydrate – water interfacial free energy obtained from CNT + Seeding calculations of Zerón *et al.* [70] and Eq. (7), is $\gamma(0) \equiv \gamma_{hw} = \gamma_{hw}(\Delta T) - \Delta\gamma_{hw} = 38 + 0.194 \times 35 \approx 45 \text{ mJ/m}^2$, which is also in excellent agreement with the value obtained in this work, $44(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we have determined the interfacial free energy between methane hydrate and liquid water using molecular dynamics simulations. To this end, we employed two recent extensions of the mold integration method, Mold Integration–Host (MI-H) and Mold Integration–Guess (MI-G), previously introduced by some of us [78, 93] to address the challenges inherent to clathrate hydrate interfaces. All calculations were conducted under thermodynamic conditions in which the hydrate and aqueous phases coexist, as required by the methodology.

Recognizing the critical role of molecular models in determining interfacial free energies, we adopted the TIP4P/Ice water model, known for its accurate prediction of the ice–water interfacial energy [100], Methane was represented as a single-site Lennard-Jones particle, using parameters from Guillot and Guissani [101] and Paschek [102]. This combination of models has been shown to reliably reproduce the hydrate dissociation line [104, 105], thus providing a robust framework for assessing interfacial properties at coexistence.

Using the MI-H and MI-G techniques, we obtained values of $43(1)$ and $44(1) \text{ mJ/m}^2$, respectively, for the CH_4 hydrate–water interfacial free energy. These results, averaging around 44 mJ/m^2 , are notably higher than the values reported for CO_2 hydrate–water and ice–water interfaces ($\sim 30 \text{ mJ/m}^2$). While the MI methodology has successfully reproduced experimental values for CO_2 hydrate [78, 93, 94] and ice [98], agreement with available experimental data for CH_4 hydrate remains less definitive. Experimental estimates span a broad range, from 28 to 40 mJ/m^2 in the studies by Uchida *et al.* [64, 65] and from 29 to 35 mJ/m^2 in those by Anderson *et al.* [66].

Nonetheless, our results are consistent with previous simulation studies employing indirect approaches based on the same molecular models [70]. Furthermore, advanced computational studies of hydrate nucleation, both by Arjun and Bolhuis [43, 45, 46, 68, 69] and by some of us [70], have demonstrated that nucleation barriers for CH_4 hydrate are significantly higher than those for CO_2 hydrate under comparable conditions, by several tens of $k_B T$. Recent results from the Seeding technique combined with CNT also support this trend [70]. These differences in nucleation behavior have been attributed to underlying disparities in interfacial free energies, reinforcing our conclusion that the CH_4 hydrate–water interfacial free energy exceeds that of its CO_2 counterpart.

In summary, our results establish molecular simulation as a powerful and reliable complementary approach for determining

interfacial free energies of hydrate systems. We demonstrate that the MI methodology enables accurate prediction of interfacial free energies for complex solid phases, including CO_2 , THF, and CH_4 hydrates. This work represents a significant step forward in the molecular-level understanding of hydrate interfaces and opens new avenues for the computational determination of interfacial properties in a broad range of hydrate materials.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Iván M. Zerón: Methodology, Investigation. **José Manuel Míguez:** Methodology, Investigation. **Jesús Algaba:** Writing – review & editing. **Bruno Mendiboure:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Felipe J. Blas:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supporting Information

Representation of configurations of simulation boxes using the MI-H technique (Section A), representation of configurations of simulation boxes using the MI-G technique (Section B), evolution of the number of water molecules in the hydrate phase induced by the MI-H model as functions of time (Section C), evolution of the number of water molecules in the hydrate phase induced by the MI-G model as functions of time (Section D), and representation of the initial configurations of simulation boxes used in this work (Section E).

Movie S1. Simulation of an aqueous slab (center) in coexistence with two methane reservoirs (sides) at 400 bar and 294 K, employing the MI-H methodology with $\varepsilon_m = 8 k_B T$, $N_w = 56$, and $r < r_w^0$ (crystallization observed). Methane molecules are shown as green spheres, water molecules as red and white lines, and the mold’s attractive interaction sites as cyan spheres. The total simulation time is 500 ns.

Movie S2. Simulation of an aqueous slab (center) in coexistence with two methane reservoirs (sides) at 400 bar and 294 K,

employing the MI-G methodology with $\varepsilon_m = 12 k_B T$, $N_w = 16$, and $r < r_w^0$ (crystallization observed). Methane molecules are shown as green spheres, water molecules as red and white lines, and the mold's attractive interaction sites as purple spheres. The total simulation time is 500 ns.

Movie S3. Simulation of an aqueous slab (center) in coexistence with two methane reservoirs (sides) at 400 bar and 294 K, employing the MI-H methodology with $\varepsilon_m = 8 k_B T$, $N_w = 56$, and $r > r_w^0$ (no crystallization observed). Methane molecules are shown as green spheres, water molecules as red and white lines, and the mold's attractive interaction sites as cyan spheres. The total simulation time is 500 ns.

Movie S4. Simulation of an aqueous slab (center) in coexistence with two methane reservoirs (sides) at 400 bar and 294 K, employing the MI-G methodology with $\varepsilon_m = 12 k_B T$, $N_w = 16$, and $r > r_w^0$ (no crystallization observed). Methane molecules are shown as green spheres, water molecules as red and white lines, and the mold's attractive interaction sites as purple spheres. The total simulation time is 500 ns.

References

- [1] B. C. Barnes, A. K. Sum, *Advances in molecular simulations of clathrate hydrates*, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Eng.* 2 (2) (2013) 184–190.
- [2] J. A. Ripmeester, S. Alavi, *Clathrate Hydrates: Molecular Science and Characterization*, Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, Germany, 2022.
- [3] J.-A. Dolyniuk, B. Owens-Baird, J. Wang, J. V. Zaikina, K. Kovnir, *Clathrate thermoelectrics*, *Mater. Sci. Eng. R. Rep.* 108 (2016) 1–46.
- [4] J. S. Kasper, P. Hagenmuller, M. Pouchard, C. Cros, *Clathrate structure of silicon Na₈Si₄₆ and Na_xSi₁₃₆ ($x < 11$)*, *Science* 150 (1965) 1713–1714.
- [5] H. Lin, S. Lee, L. Sun, M. Spellings, M. Engel, S. C. Glotzer, C. A. Mirkin, *Clathrate colloidal crystals*, *Science* 355 (2017) 931–935.
- [6] S. Lee, E. G. Teich, M. Engel, S. C. Glotzer, *Entropic colloidal crystallization pathways via fluid–fluid transitions and multidimensional prenucleation motifs*, *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci. USA* 116 (2019) 14843–14851.
- [7] W. L. Mao, H. K. Mao, A. F. Goncharov, V. V. Struzhkin, Q. Guo, J. Hu, J. Shu, R. J. Hemley, M. Somayazulu, Y. Zhao, *Hydrogen clusters in clathrate hydrate*, *Science* 297 (2002) 2247–2249.
- [8] E. D. Sloan, *Fundamental principles and applications of natural gas hydrates*, *Science* 426 (2003) 353–359.
- [9] C. A. Koh, A. K. Sum, E. D. Sloan, *State of the art: Natural gas hydrates as a natural resource*, *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* 8 (2012) 132–138.
- [10] Z. R. Chong, S. H. B. Yang, P. Babu, P. Linga, X.-S. Li, *Review of natural gas hydrates as an energy resource: Prospects and challenges*, *Appl. Energy* 162 (2016) 1633–1652.
- [11] J. Zheng, Z. R. Chong, M. F. Qureshi, P. Linga, *Carbon dioxide sequestration via gas hydrates: a potential pathway toward decarbonization*, *Energy & Fuels* 34 (9) (2020) 10529–10546.
- [12] C. Bourry, J.-L. Charlou, J.-P. Donval, M. Brunelli, C. Focsa, B. Chazallon, *X-ray synchrotron diffraction study of natural gas hydrates from african margin*, *Geophysical Research Letters* 34 (22) (2007).
- [13] M. Yousuf, S. Qadri, D. Knies, K. Grabowski, R. Coffin, J. Pohlman, *Novel results on structural investigations of natural minerals of clathrate hydrates*, *Applied Physics A* 78 (2004) 925–939.
- [14] Y. F. Makogon, *Hydrates of hydrocarbons*, PennWell Publishing Co., Tulsa, OK, 1997.
- [15] H. Aghajari, M. H. Moghaddam, M. Zallaghi, *Study of effective parameters for enhancement of methane gas production from natural gas hydrate reservoirs*, *Green Energy & Environment* 4 (4) (2019) 453–469.
- [16] A. Y. Manakov, S. V. Goryainov, A. V. Kurnosov, A. Y. Likhacheva, Y. A. Dyadin, E. G. Larionov, *Clathrate nature of the high-pressure tetrahydrofuran hydrate phase and some new data on the phase diagram of the tetrahydrofuran–water system at pressures up to 3 GPa*, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 107 (2003) 7861–7866.
- [17] T. Makino, T. Sugahara, K. Ohgaki, *Stability boundaries of tetrahydrofuran + water system*, *J. Chem. Eng. Data* 50 (2005) 2058–2060.
- [18] K. A. Kvenvolden, *Methane hydrate – a major reservoir of carbon in the shallow geosphere?*, *Chem. Geol.* 71 (1988) 41–51.
- [19] S. Choi, J. H. Drese, C. W. Jones, *Methane exploitation by carbon dioxide from gas hydrates—phase equilibria for CO₂-CH₄ mixed hydrate system*, *J. Chem. Eng. Jpn.* 29 (1996) 478–483.
- [20] M. Yand, Y. Song, L. Jiang, Y. Zhao, X. Ruan, Y. Zhang, S. Wang, *Hydrate-based technology for CO₂ capture from fossil fuel power plants*, *Appl. Energy* 116 (2014) 26–40.
- [21] M. Ricaurte, C. Dicharry, X. Renaud, J.-P. Torré, *Combination of surfactants and organic compounds for boosting CO₂ separation from natural gas by clathrate hydrate formation*, *Fuel* 122 (2014) 206–217.
- [22] B. Kvamme, G. A. T. Buanes, T. Kuznetsova, G. Erslund, *Storage of CO₂ in natural gas hydrate reservoirs and the effect of hydrate as an extra sealing in cold aquifers*, *Int. J. Greenhouse Gas Control* 1 (2007) 236–246.
- [23] V. Chihaua, S. Adams, W. F. Kuhs, *Molecular dynamics simulations of properties of a (001) methane clathrate hydrate surface*, *Chem. Phys.* 317 (2005) 208–225. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemphys.2005.05.024>.
- [24] B. Peters, N. E. R. Zimmermann, G. T. Beckham, J. W. Tester, B. J. Trout, *Path sampling calculation of methane diffusivity in natural gas hydrates from a water-vacancy assisted mechanism*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 130 (2008) 17342–17350. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1021/ja802014m>.
- [25] N. J. English, J. S. Tse, *Mechanisms for thermal conduction in methane hydrate*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 103 (2009) 015901. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.103.015901>.
- [26] P. G. Debenedetti, *Metastable Liquids: Concepts and Principles*, Princeton University Press, 1996.
- [27] D. Kashchiev, *Nucleation*, Butterworth-Heinemann: Oxford, UK, 2000.
- [28] N. Maeda, *Nucleation of Gas Hydrates*, Springer Nature Switzerland, Switzerland, 2020.
- [29] D. Kashchiev, A. Firoozabadi, *Driving force for crystallization of gas hydrates*, *J. Cryst. Growth* 241 (2002) 220–230.
- [30] D. Kashchiev, A. Firoozabadi, *Nucleation of gas hydrates*, *J. Cryst. Growth* 243 (2002) 476–489.
- [31] L. C. Jacobson, W. Hujo, V. Molinero, *Amorphous precursors in the nucleation of clathrate hydrates*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 132 (2010) 11806–11811.
- [32] L. C. Jacobson, W. Hujo, V. Molinero, *Nucleation pathways of clathrate hydrates: Effect of guest size and solubility*, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 114 (2010) 13796–13807.
- [33] M. R. Walsh, G. T. Beckham, C. A. Koh, E. D. Sloan, D. T. Wu, A. K. Sum, *Methane hydrate nucleation rates from molecular dynamics simulations: Effects of aqueous methane concentration, interfacial curvature, and system size*, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 115 (2011) 21241. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1021/jp206483q>.
- [34] L. C. Jacobson, V. Molinero, *Can amorphous nuclei grow crystalline clathrates? The size and crystallinity of critical clathrate nuclei*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (2011) 6458–6463.
- [35] S. Sarupria, P. G. Debenedetti, *Molecular dynamics study of carbon dioxide hydrate dissociation*, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 3 (2012) 2942–2947.
- [36] B. C. Knott, V. Molinero, M. F. Doherty, B. Peters, *Homogeneous nucleation of methane hydrates: Unrealistic under realistic conditions*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 134 (2012) 19544–19547.
- [37] S. Sarupria, P. G. Debenedetti, *Homogeneous nucleation of methane hydrate in microsecond molecular dynamics simulations*, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 115 (2011) 6102–6111.
- [38] S. Liang, P. G. Kusalik, *Nucleation of gas hydrates within constant energy systems*, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 117 (2013) 1403–1410. doi:<https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jp308395x>.
- [39] B. C. Barnes, B. C. Knott, G. T. Beckham, D. Wu, A. K. Sum, *Molecular dynamics study of carbon dioxide hydrate dissociation*, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 118 (2014) 13236–13243. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1021/jp507959q>.
- [40] D. Yuhara, B. C. Barnes, D. Suh, B. C. Knott, G. T. Beckham, K. Yasuoka, D. Wu, A. K. Sum, *Nucleation rate analysis of methane hydrate from molecular dynamics simulations*, *Faraday Discuss.* 179 (2015) 463–474. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1039/c4fd00219a>.
- [41] P. Warriar, M. N. Khan, V. Srivastava, C. M. Maupin, C. A. Koh,

- Overview: Nucleation of clathrate hydrates, *J. Chem. Phys.* 145 (2016) 211705. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4968590>.
- [42] Z. Zhang, P. G. Kusalik, G.-J. Guo, Molecular insight into the growth of hydrogen and methane binary hydrates, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 122 (2018) 7771–7778. doi:[10.1021/acs.jpcc.8b00842](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.8b00842).
- [43] Arjun, T. A. Berendsen, P. G. Bolhuis, Unbiased atomistic insight in the competing nucleation mechanisms of methane hydrates, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 116 (2019) 19305–19310. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1906502116>.
- [44] Z. Zhang, G.-J. Guo, N. Wu, P. G. Kusalik, Molecular insights into guest and composition dependence of mixed hydrate nucleation, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 124 (2020) 25078–25086. doi:[10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c07375](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c07375).
- [45] A. Arjun, P. G. Bolhuis, Rate prediction for homogeneous nucleation of methane hydrate at moderate supersaturation using transition interface sampling, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 124 (2020) 8099–8109. doi:<https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c04582>.
- [46] A. Arjun, P. G. Bolhuis, Homogeneous nucleation rate of CO₂ hydrates using transition interface sampling, *J. Chem. Phys.* 154 (2021) 164507.
- [47] L. Wang, K. Hall, Z. Chang, P. G. Kusalik, Mixed hydrate nucleation: molecular mechanics and cage structures, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 126 (2022) 7015–7026. doi:[10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c03223](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c03223).
- [48] J. Grabowska, S. Blázquez, E. Sanz, I. M. Zerón, J. Algaba, J. M. Míguez, F. J. Blas, C. Vega, Solubility of methane in water: some useful results for hydrate nucleation, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 126 (2022) 8553–8570.
- [49] J. Grabowska, S. Blázquez, E. Sanz, E. G. Noya, I. M. Zerón, J. Algaba, J. M. Míguez, F. J. Blas, C. Vega, Homogeneous nucleation rate of methane hydrate formation under experimental conditions from seeding simulations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 158 (11) (2023) 114505.
- [50] J. Algaba, I. M. Zerón, J. M. Míguez, J. Grabowska, S. Blázquez, E. Sanz, C. Vega, F. J. Blas, Solubility of carbon dioxide in water: Some useful results for hydrate nucleation, *J. Chem. Phys.* 158 (18) (2023) 054505.
- [51] L. Wang, P. G. Kusalik, Understanding why constant energy or constant temperature may affect nucleation behavior in MD simulations: A study of gas hydrate nucleation, *J. Chem. Phys.* 159 (2023) 184501. doi:[10.1063/5.0169669](https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0169669).
- [52] E. Sanz, J. R. Espinosa, R. Caballero-Bernal, J. L. F. Abascal, C. Valeriani, Homogeneous ice nucleation at moderate supercooling from molecular simulation, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (2013) 15008–15017.
- [53] J. R. Espinosa, C. Navarro, E. Sanz, C. Valeriani, C. Vega, On the time required to freeze water, *J. Chem. Phys.* 145 (2016) 211922.
- [54] J. R. Espinosa, C. Vega, C. Valeriani, E. Sanz, Seeding approach to crystal nucleation, *J. Chem. Phys.* 144 (2016) 034501.
- [55] G. D. Soria, J. R. Espinosa, J. Ramirez, C. Valeriani, C. Vega, E. Sanz, A simulation study of homogeneous ice nucleation in supercooled salty water, *J. Chem. Phys.* 148 (2018) 222811.
- [56] W. Lechner, C. Dellago, Accurate determination of crystal structures based on averaged local bond order parameters, *J. Chem. Phys.* 129 (2008) 114707.
- [57] Z. M. Aman, C. A. Koh, Interfacial phenomena in gas hydrate systems, *Chemical Society Reviews* 45 (6) (2016) 1678–1690. doi:[10.1039/C5CS00791G](https://doi.org/10.1039/C5CS00791G).
- [58] A. W. Adamson, A. P. Gast, *Physical Chemistry of Surfaces*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1997.
- [59] R. D. Weir, E. Th. W. de Loos, Measurement of the Thermodynamic Properties of Multiple Phases, Vol. VII, *Experimental Thermodynamics*, Elsevier, 2005, Ch. 15, M. J. B. Evans, *Measurement of Surface and Interfacial Tensions*.
- [60] T. Young, III. An essay on the cohesion of fluids, *Philos. Trans. R. Soc.* 95 (1805) 65–87.
- [61] Y. P. Handa, D. Stupin, Thermodynamic properties and dissociation characteristics of methane and propane hydrates in 70-Å-radius silica gel pores, *J. Phys. Chem.* 96 (1992) 8599–8603.
- [62] M. B. Clennell, M. Hovland, J. S. Booth, P. Henry, W. J. Winters, Formation of natural gas hydrates in marine sediments 1. conceptual model of gas hydrate growth conditioned by host sediment properties, *J. Geophys. Res.* 104 (1999) 22,985–23,003.
- [63] P. Henry, M. Thomas, M. B. Clennell, Formation of natural gas hydrates in marine sediments 2. thermodynamic calculations of stability conditions in porous sediments, *J. Phys. Chem.* 96 (1992) 23,005–23,022.
- [64] T. Uchida, T. Ebinuma, T. Ishizaki, Dissociation condition measurements of methane hydrate in confined small pores of porous glass, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 103 (1999) 3659–3662.
- [65] T. Uchida, T. Ebinuma, S. Takeya, J. Nagao, H. Narita, Effects of pore sizes on dissociation temperatures and pressures of methane, carbon dioxide, and propane hydrates in porous media, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 106 (2002) 802–826.
- [66] R. Anderson, M. Llamedo, B. Tohihi, R. W. Burgass, Characteristics of clathrate hydrate equilibria in mesopores and interpretation of experimental data, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 107 (2003) 3500–3506.
- [67] R. Anderson, M. Llamedo, B. Tohihi, R. W. Burgass, Experimental measurement of methane and carbon dioxide clathrate hydrate equilibria in mesoporous silica, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 107 (2003) 3507–3514.
- [68] A. Arjun, P. G. Bolhuis, Molecular understanding of homogeneous nucleation of CO₂ hydrates using transition path sampling, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 125 (2021) 338–349.
- [69] A. Arjun, P. G. Bolhuis, Homogeneous nucleation of crystalline methane hydrate in molecular dynamics transition paths sampled under realistic conditions, *J. Chem. Phys.* 158 (2023) 044504.
- [70] I. M. Zerón, J. Algaba, J. M. Míguez, J. Grabowska, S. Blázquez, E. Sanz, C. Vega, F. J. Blas, Homogeneous nucleation rate of carbon dioxide hydrate formation under experimental condition from seeding simulations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 162 (2025) 134708.
- [71] N. D. Pasquale, J. Algaba, P. M. de Hijes, I. Sanchez-Burgos, A. R. Tejedor, S. R. Yeandel, F. J. Blas, R. L. Davidchack, J. R. Espinosa, C. L. Freeman, J. H. Harding, B. B. Laird, E. Sanz, C. Vega, L. Rovigatti, Solid-liquid interfacial free energy from computer simulations: Challenges and recent advances, *Chem. Rev.* 125 (2025) 5003–5053.
- [72] J. W. Gibbs, On the equilibrium of heterogeneous substances, *Trans. Conn. Acad. Sci.* 3 (1876) 108–248.
- [73] M. Volmer, A. Weber, Keimbildung in übersättigten gebilden, *Zeitschrift für physikalische Chemie* 119 (1) (1926) 277–301.
- [74] R. Becker, W. Döring, Kinetische behandlung der keimbildung in übersättigten dämpfen, *Annalen der physik* 416 (8) (1935) 719–752.
- [75] K. F. Kelton, Crystal nucleation in liquids and glasses, in: *Solid state physics*, Vol. 45, Elsevier, 1991, pp. 75–177.
- [76] L. C. Jacobson, W. Hujo, V. Molinero, Nucleation pathways of clathrate hydrates: Effect of guest size and solubility, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 114 (2010) 13796–13807.
- [77] J. Grabowska, S. Blázquez, E. Sanz, E. G. Noya, I. M. Zerón, J. Algaba, J. M. Míguez, F. J. Blas, C. Vega, Homogeneous nucleation rate of methane hydrate formation under experimental conditions from seeding simulations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 158 (11) (2023) 114505.
- [78] J. Algaba, E. Acuña, J. M. Míguez, B. Mendiboure, I. M. Zerón, F. J. Blas, Simulation of the carbon dioxide hydrate-water interfacial energy, *J. Colloid Interf. Sci.* 623 (2022) 354–367. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2022.05.029>.
- [79] J. Miyazaki, J. A. Barker, G. M. Pound, A new monte carlo method for calculating surface tension, *J. Chem. Phys.* 64 (1976) 3364–3369.
- [80] J. Q. Broughton, G. H. Gilmer, Molecular dynamics investigation of the crystal-fluid interface. vi. excess surface free energies of crystal-liquid systems, *J. Chem. Phys.* 84 (1986) 5759–5768.
- [81] R. L. Davidchack, B. B. Laird, Direct calculation of the Hard-Sphere crystal/melt interfacial free energy, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 85 (2000) 4752–4754.
- [82] R. L. Davidchack, J. R. Morris, B. B. Laird, The anisotropic hard-sphere crystal-melt interfacial free energy from fluctuations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 125 (2006) 094710.
- [83] R. L. Davidchack, Hard spheres revisited: Accurate calculation of the solid-liquid interfacial free energy, *J. Chem. Phys.* 133 (2010) 234701.
- [84] R. Handel, R. L. Davidchack, Direct calculation of solid-liquid interfacial free energy for molecular systems: TIP4P/Ice-water interface, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 100 (2008) 036104.
- [85] R. L. Davidchack, R. Handel, J. Anwar, A. V. Brukhno, Ice ih-water interfacial free energy of simple water models with full electrostatic interactions, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* 8 (2012) 2383–2390.
- [86] R. K. R. Addula, S. N. Punnathanam, Computation of solid-fluid interfacial free energy in molecular systems using thermodynamic integration, *J. Chem. Phys.* 153 (2020) 154504.
- [87] S. R. Yeandel, C. L. Freeman, J. H. Harding, A general method for calculating solid/liquid interfacial free energies from atomistic simulations: Application to caso₄ · x h₂o, *J. Chem. Phys.* 157 (2022) 084117.

- [88] F. Leroy, D. J. Dos Santos, F. Müller-Plathe, Interfacial excess free energies of solid-liquid interfaces by molecular dynamics simulation and thermodynamic integration, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* 30 (2009) 864–870.
- [89] F. Leroy, F. Müller-Plathe, Solid-liquid surface free energy of lennard-jones liquid on smooth and rough surfaces computed by molecular dynamics using the phantom-wall method, *J. Chem. Phys.* 133 (2010) 044110.
- [90] F. Leroy, F. Müller-Plathe, Dry-surface simulation method for the determination of the work of adhesion of solid-liquid interfaces, *Langmuir* 31 (2015) 8335–8345.
- [91] S. Angioletti-Uberti, M. Ceriotti, P. D. Lee, M. W. Finnis, Solid-liquid interface free energy through metadynamics simulations, *Phys. Rev. B* 81 (2010) 125416–1–125416–11.
- [92] J. W. Cahn, American Society of Metals, Metals Park, Ohio, 1979, Ch. Thermodynamics of Solid and Fluid Surfaces, pp. 17–18.
- [93] I. M. Zerón, J. M. Míguez, B. Mendiboure, J. Algaba, F. J. Blas, Simulation of the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial energy: The mold integration–guest methodology, *J. Chem. Phys.* 157 (2022) 134709. doi:https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0101746.
- [94] C. Romero-Guzmán, I. M. Zerón, J. Algaba, B. Mendiboure, J. M. Míguez, F. J. Blas, Effect of pressure on the carbon dioxide hydrate–water interfacial free energy along its dissociation line, *J. Chem. Phys.* 158 (2023) 194704.
- [95] M. J. Torrejón, C. Romero-Guzmán, M. M. Piñeiro, F. J. Blas, J. Algaba, Simulation of the THF hydrate - water interfacial free energy from computer simulation, *J. Chem. Phys.* 161 (2024) 064701.
- [96] J. R. Espinosa, C. Vega, E. Sanz, The mold integration method for the calculation of the crystal-fluid interfacial free energy from simulations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 141 (2014) 134709.
- [97] J. R. Espinosa, C. Vega, C. Valeriani, E. Sanz, The crystal-fluid interfacial free energy and nucleation rate of nacl from different simulation methods, *J. Chem. Phys.* 142 (2015) 194709.
- [98] J. R. Espinosa, C. Vega, E. Sanz, Ice - water interfacial free energy for the TIP4P, TIP4P/2005, TIP4P/Ice, and mW models as obtained from the Mold Integration technique, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 120 (2016) 8068–8075.
- [99] I. Zerón, C. Vega, A. Benavides, Continuous version of a square-well potential of variable range and its application in molecular dynamics simulations, *Mol. Phys.* 116 (21-22) (2018) 3355–3365.
- [100] J. L. F. Abascal, E. Sanz, R. G. Fernández, C. Vega, A potential model for the study of ices and amorphous water: TIP4P/Ice, *J. Chem. Phys.* 122 (2005) 234511.
- [101] B. Guillot, Y. Guissani, A computer simulation study of the temperature dependence of the hydrophobic hydration, *J. Chem. Phys.* 99 (10) (1993) 8075–8094. doi:10.1063/1.465634. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.465634>
- [102] D. Paschek, Temperature dependence of the hydrophobic hydration and interaction of simple solutes: An examination of five popular water models, *J. Chem. Phys.* 120 (14) (2004) 6674–6690. doi:10.1063/1.1652015. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1652015>
- [103] W. L. Jorgensen, J. D. Madura, C. J. Swenson, Optimized intermolecular potential functions for liquid hydrocarbons, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 106 (1984) 6638–6646. doi:10.1021/ja00334a030.
- [104] M. M. Conde, C. Vega, Determining the three-phase coexistence line in methane hydrates using computer simulations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 133 (6) (2010) 064507. doi:https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3466751.
- [105] M. M. Conde, C. Vega, Note: A simple correlation to locate the three phase coexistence line in methane-hydrate simulations, *J. Chem. Phys.* 138 (5) (2013) 056101. doi:https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4790647.
- [106] V. K. Michalis, J. Costandy, I. N. Tsimpanogiannis, A. K. Stubos, I. G. Economou, Prediction of the phase equilibria of methane hydrates using the direct phase coexistence methodology, *J. Chem. Phys.* 142 (4) (2015) 044501. doi:https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4905572.
- [107] S. Blazquez, J. Algaba, J. M. Míguez, C. Vega, F. J. Blas, M. M. Conde, Three-phase equilibria of hydrates from computer simulation. I: Finite-size effects in the methane hydrate, *J. Chem. Phys.* 160 (16) (2024) 164721.
- [108] A. M. Fernández-Fernández, M. Pérez-Rodríguez, A. Comesaña, M. M. Piñeiro, Three-phase equilibrium curve shift for methane hydrate in oceanic conditions calculated from molecular dynamics simulations, *J. Mol. Liq.* 274 (2019) 426–433. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2018.10.146.
- [109] D. van der Spoel, E. Lindahl, B. Hess, G. Groenhof, A. E. Mark, H. J. Berendsen, Gromacs: Fast, flexible, and free, *J. Comput. Chem.* 26 (16) (2005) 1701–1718.
- [110] D. Frenkel, B. Smit, *Understanding Molecular Simulations*, 2nd Ed. Academic, San Diego, 2002.
- [111] E. G. Noya, C. Vega, E. de Miguel, Determination of the melting point of hard spheres from direct coexistence simulation methods, *J. Chem. Phys.* 128 (2008) 154507. doi:https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2901172.
- [112] D. Frenkel, *Simulations: The dark side*, *Eur. Phys. J. Plus* 128 (10) (2013) 1–21. doi:https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/i2013-13010-8.
- [113] J. R. Espinosa, E. Sanz, C. Valeriani, C. Vega, On fluid-solid direct coexistence simulations: The pseudo-hard sphere model, *J. Chem. Phys.* 139 (2013) 144502. doi:https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4823499.
- [114] M. P. Allen, D. J. Tildesley, *Computer Simulation of Liquids*, 2nd Ed., Clarendon, Oxford, 2017.
- [115] M. A. Cuendet, W. F. V. Gunsteren, On the calculation of velocity-dependent properties in molecular dynamics simulations using the leapfrog integration algorithm, *J. Chem. Phys.* 127 (2007) 184102.
- [116] S. Nosé, A molecular dynamics method for simulations in the canonical ensemble, *Mol. Phys.* 52 (1984) 255–268.
- [117] M. Parrinello, A. Rahman, Polymorphic transitions in single crystals: A new molecular dynamics method, *J. Appl. Phys.* 52 (1981) 7182–7190.
- [118] U. Essmann, L. Perera, M. L. Berkowitz, T. Darden, H. Lee, L. G. Pedersen, A smooth particle mesh Ewald method, *J. Chem. Phys.* 103 (1995) 8577–8593.
- [119] I. M. Zerón, J. Algaba, J. M. Míguez, B. Mendiboure, F. J. Blas, Rotationally invariant local bond order parameters for accurate determination of hydrate structures, *Molecular Physics* 122 (21-22) (2024) e2395438.
- [120] I. Sanchez-Burgos, E. Sanz, C. Vega, J. R. Espinosa, Fcc vs. hcp competition in colloidal hard-sphere nucleation: on their relative stability, interfacial free energy and nucleation rate, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 23 (2021) 19611–19626. doi:10.1039/D1CP01784E.
- [121] V. Molinero, E. B. Moore, Water modeled as an intermediate element between carbon and silicon, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 113 (2009) 4008–4016. doi:https://doi.org/10.1021/jp805227c.
- [122] L. C. Jacobson, V. Molinero, A methane-water model for coarse-grained simulations of solutions and clathrate hydrates, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 114 (2010) 7302–7311.
- [123] Z. D. D. L. Y. Chen, R. Sun, The influence of temperature, pressure, salinity and capillary force on the formation of methane hydrate, *Geosci. Front.* 2 (2011) 125–135.
- [124] D. Jin, J. Zhong, Reparameterization of the mw model to accurately predict the experimental phase diagram of methane hydrate, *J. Chem. Phys.* 161 (2024) 174504.
- [125] D. Kashchiev, G. M. van Rosmalen, Review: Nucleation in solutions revisited, *Cryst. Res. Technol.* 38 (2003) 555–574. doi:https://doi.org/10.1002/crat.200310070.
- [126] J. W. Gibbs, On the equilibrium of heterogeneous substances, *Trans. Conn. Acad.* 3 (1877) 343.
- [127] J. Espinosa, E. Sanz, C. Valeriani, C. Vega, Homogeneous ice nucleation evaluated for several water models, *J. Chem. Phys.* 141 (2014) 18C529.
- [128] P. M. de Hijes, J. R. Espinosa, E. Sanz, C. Vega, Interfacial free energy of a liquid-solid interface: Its change with curvature, *J. Chem. Phys.* 151 (2019) 144501.